

Table 1. Performance of 4 varieties in 3 locations in Zaire, 1977-80.

Location	Mean yield (t/ha)					% over local check R66				
	R66	C4-1-5	RY1	RY2	RY7	C4-1-5	RY1	RY2	RY7	
Yangambi	2.5	2.8	3.3	2.8	2.6	8	30	12	2	
Bambesa	3.0	—	3.9	4.0	3.4	—	30	34	14	
Boketa	1.8	—	2.3	2.0	2.3	—	23	10	23	

Table 2. Main characters of 5 varieties at Yangambi, Zaire.

Characteristic	R66	C4-1-5	RY1 (IRAT2)	RY2 (IRAT8)	RY7 (IRAT13)
Origin	Local	Local	Côte d'Ivoire	Côte d'Ivoire	Côte d'Ivoire
<i>Characteristics</i>					
Duration (d)	120	115	120	125	130
Plant height (cm)	166	162	142	141	110
Lodging (score)	5	5	3	3	1
<i>Grain characters</i>					
Length (mm)	9.2	9.5	9.8	8.6	10.8
Width (mm)	3.0	3.0	3.1	2.8	3.6
Thickness (mm)	2.0	2.1	2.1	2.0	2.0
L/W ratio	3.1	3.2	3.2	3.0	3.0
L/T ratio	1.5	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.8
1000-grain weight	32.0	34.1	37.9	24.7	39.0
Translucency (%)	82.0	72.0	57.3	60.9	59.8
Leaf blast reaction	Moderately susceptible	Resistant	Resistant	Resistant	Resistant

locations where strong winds frequently induce severe losses. It is also more resistant to leaf blast. All other characters are good (Table 2).

RY1 was released in Zaire in 1982 to replace R66. □

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Seed technology

Modified roll-towel method to determine rice seed vigor

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The International Seed Testing Association recommends the roll-towel method to test germination of small and medium size seeds. But seedling growth varies considerably with this method. We developed a modified roll-towel (MRT) method that allows unobstructed root growth for a more reliable estimate of seed vigor.

The germination test was made on a 30-cm × 20-cm 600-gauge polythene sheet. Presoaked 2-cm × 20-cm germination paper strips were spread evenly over the top of the polythene sheet. Seeds were placed in a single row, embryo side down, on the germination paper and held in position by covering them with another presoaked

germination paper strip, gently pressed down. Germination paper cut to the size of the polythene sheet was spread over all. The polythene sheet with the seeds was rolled lengthwise and secured with rubber bands on either end. The roll was kept slanted inside a medium-size plastic container containing 2-3 cm deep water.

Growth of 10-d-old seedlings and the variability between the 2 test methods are given in the table. Seedling growth improved with little variability.

The MRT method has these advantages:

- Seedlings showed uniform growth;
- Roots grow downward without coiling or curling on the paper;

Growth and variability of 10-d-old rice seedlings.^a Aduthurai, India.

Growth parameter	Rolled towel	Modified rolled towel
Germination (%)	91.2 ± 1.4	93.7 ± 1.2
Root length (mm)	174.6 ± 12.3	192.4 ± 2.1
Shoot length (mm)	103.7 ± 11.7	106.6 ± 3.9
Dry mass (mg/10 seedlings)	116.7 ± 9.9	126.6 ± 2.2

^aMean ± SD of 10 samples.

- Capillary movement of water prevents waterlogging;
- No need to add water during germination unless water in the container dries up;
- Less time-consuming and occupies little space in the germination cabinet;
- Equally good for small and medium size seeds; and
- Cheaper than other methods and materials required are easily available.

Root growth is partially visible from outside and the roll can be unfurled when needed. □

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